

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN ENGINEERING UNIVERSITIES

Sh. R. Mahammadjonov.

Student, Andijan Machine Building Institute

K. Z. Ziyayeva.

Teacher, Andijan Machine Building Institute

ANNOTATION. This article analyzes the problems of teaching ESP in engineering universities and discusses some difficulties with the translation of terms

АННОТАЦИЯ. В данной статье анализируются проблемы преподавания ESP в инженерных вузах и обсуждаются некоторые трудности с переводом терминов

Significant changes in the structure of higher education and the transition to a three-level system of education (bachelor's, master's and postgraduate studies) have led to changes in the methods and means of teaching students in higher education institutions. These changes are especially noticeable at the master's and postgraduate levels. There are great advantages in a multi-level learning process that allows developing skills and abilities in a logical and successive form, based on a competency-based approach [1, 2]. In addition, it is necessary to note the presence of conscious professional goals for undergraduates and graduate students who make their choice in favor of continuing their education based on the knowledge, experience and interests gained.

In accordance with the requirements of new educational standards, when teaching a foreign language at an engineering university, it is necessary to take into account the professionally oriented component of foreign language training for graduate and undergraduate students, which includes knowledge of terminology and the ability to use it to solve professional and academic problems.

Modern computer technologies allow students to quickly and effortlessly translate a huge amount of foreign text, create a terminological dictionary, which significantly reduces the quality of the educational process. In addition, modern students belonging to generation do not like to deal with routine translation from a foreign language into Uzbek. The younger generation tends to quickly complete a certain amount of work and switch to more interesting tasks.

We were tasked with getting students interested in learning a foreign language and at the same time expanding their stock of professionally oriented foreign words. After analyzing the psychological characteristics of the younger generation, we came to the conclusion that modern students:

- 1) are aimed at obtaining professional knowledge;
- 2) are well versed in the field of future professional activity;
- 3) love interactive teaching methods;
- 4) are ready to use computer programs and Internet resources for learning.

The constantly developing world and man are in close proximity. Man actively transforms the surrounding reality. The mediator between a person and the cognized world is the language, which "creates opportunities for streamlining and systematizing in memory a lot of knowledge in order to build a linguistic picture of the world characteristic of each given ethno-cultural collective."

In the active life of our republic in the 21st century, the process of colossal global transformations is actively going on, affecting all spheres of industry. One of the leading branches of mechanical engineering in many countries of the world is the automotive industry. The industry terminology is becoming increasingly in demand and is of paramount importance in the current situation.

The most important measures to fundamentally improve the foreign language education system in the republic are considered as the most a significant task. Also, strengthening and developing the material base for students and specialists, the state ensures their introduction into the world achievement of science and technology, organizes their mass education, and qualification courses, the same obtaining effective results. There was a need to change the educational system ESP

(English for Specific Purposes) - English for engineering areas in higher educational institutions with new pedagogical progressive technologies. Therefore, the ESP curriculum in mechanical engineering at all levels of education should ensure the continuity, consistency and cyclicity of training, as well as the requirements of analysis the needs of the rapid growth of the market.

In our life, there are constantly terms related to the automotive industry, the technical device of the car, as well as various machines and mechanisms used both at home, for personal use, and in production. Today, knowledge of these terms is no longer mandatory.

Only for specialists, but also for ordinary people who have a personal car or agricultural machinery. At present, cars and agricultural machinery of foreign manufacturers are the most popular. It is not surprising that the flow of technical documentation, various recommendations for repair and maintenance vehicles and other mechanical and electrical technical devices written in English.

Unfortunately, at present, the features of the translation of English technical terms have not been studied enough. There are not enough special dictionaries and glossaries of similar terminology, and in the translation of technical documents related to vehicle maintenance and agricultural machinery reveals annoying errors and inaccuracies that can lead to very serious troubles and even tragedies.

One of the difficulties in translating the term in texts on the automotive industry from English into Uzbek is the ambiguity of the term, therefore Finding the correct translation of a term corresponding to a given specific text is possible only when you are well versed in the essence of the material being translated. The same term can be used in various fields of science and technology, but its translation will depend on the area in which it is used. So, for example, the term *valve* designates an electronic lamp, a faucet in heat engineering, a valve in engine building, instrument making, hydraulics.

Literatures

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